

THE INFLUENCE OF BRICK-TO-CLICK SHIFT MOTIVATIONS OF OMNI CHANNEL SUPERMARKET CONSUMERS ON THEIR ONLINE REPEAT PURCHASE: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF CONSUMER SATISFACTION AND PERCEIVED ONLINE RISK

PRIYADHARSHINI. R*

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, D. B. Jain College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.
E-mail- priyarajendran.1985@gmail.com

SUNITHA. T

Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, PT MGR Government Arts and Science College (AU) Puthur, Sirkali Tamil Nadu. E-mail- sunitha.au@gmail.com

Abstract

In the context of trust-satisfaction-repurchase intention in the Omni channel supermarket, this study examines the considerable impact of the brick-to-click transition on consumers' online repeat purchase behaviour as well as the moderating effect of consumers' neurotic tendencies. Additionally, a combination of structural equation models (SEM) and prediction-oriented segmentation (POS) was used to uncover the likely underlying heterogeneous traits of consumers. The results of the global model SEM analysis show that offline-to-online trust transference occurs in e-commerce and that this transference of trust greatly affects consumers' pleasure and their propensity to make repeat purchases. A model of the factors that influence consumers' plans to make additional online purchases is created and empirically tested. Responses to a structured, self-administered survey completed by a sample of 458 consumers served as the basis for the model test's data. The findings demonstrate that habitual loyalty—defined as respondents' propensity to shop at supermarkets as a habit or typical daily activity—significantly affects customer happiness. This suggests that customers who often purchase at a supermarket are more likely to be pleased with their online shopping experience. It was discovered that the respondents who were more likely to purchase online in order to prevent contracting COVID were happier with their online shopping experience when utilising the supermarket's website or app. The respondents who are pleased with their online shopping experience see less danger in switching to the supermarket's online channel.

Keywords: Repeat purchase intention, brick-to-click, Satisfaction, supermarket, online purchase.

INTRODUCTION

Shopping is the process of choosing a retailer and making a purchase. According to the environment they are in while shopping and how involved they are, shoppers' behaviours vary. Shopping is influenced by the type of goods, the level of perceived risk associated with the product category, and the amount of information consumers have access to regarding alternatives. Every transaction involves some or all of a process that follows a consistent pattern of see-touch-sense-select, according to observations of customer behaviour in the store. The decision-making process and the elements influencing it can both be examined while analysing the shopping decision-making process.

A repeat purchase is when a customer buys the same brand of product that they previously purchased. Recurring purchases show how loyal a buyer is to a particular brand. Additionally, it gives marketers the chance to create enduring client relationships. Repeat business is a sign of a happy and "well-retained" customer, which lowers the cost of acquiring new customers and raises overall profitability. Digital loyalty programmes, great customer service, and web and social media advertising can all help the company's repeat customer rate rise.

Repeat purchase behaviour occurs when a customer makes repeated purchases of a specific brand. It is frequently employed to gauge consumer brand loyalty. The continuation of a consumer's post-buy activity is repeat purchase behaviour. For consumers to make recurring purchases, satisfaction is essential. Repeat purchases by customers are crucial for developing brand loyalty. Age, income, education, and employment were the demographic repeat buy drivers. Value for money, brand trust, and brand effect were the particular repeat purchase drivers. The factors of price, quality, and pricing affect how often consumers make the same purchases. Consumers' intent to make a purchase is influenced by the retail environment.

Companies that were born in the digital age have significantly changed how customers interact with brands and make purchases. They have been successful in influencing others, creating a positive initial impression, and continuously exceeding client expectations. This has been made possible by the fact that these companies are built to give customers a seamless purchasing experience. Traditional retailers must embrace a strong multichannel strategy by modernising their systems and reexamining their business strategies in order to stay competitive.

With a sophisticated unified commerce and retail operations system, Brick and Click provides a superior shopping experience that combines in-store and online buying. Personalized insight, customer experience, and fulfilment across channels are being driven, and deep operational insights are being provided to assist merchants succeed in the new digital economy. Brick & Click, a hybrid cloud ready platform, combines pre-built business operations for particular retail segments with retail-specific commerce, mobile, IoT, analytics, and ERP systems to ensure that customers are always put first.

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the simplest and most reliable measures of consumer loyalty is repeat business. Aaker's brand loyalty pyramid (Aaker, 1991) states that recurrent purchases are made by customers who have reached the second level of the pyramid, also known as satisfied or habitual purchasers, depending on a variety of criteria, including prior experiences. In order to build brand loyalty, customers must engage with the business or brand on a consistent basis and become ardent supporters (Curtis et al., 2011). The current study therefore concentrated on the most obvious loyalty indicator, i.e., repeat buy behaviour, which denotes the customer's act of repurchasing from the same supermarket's online channel (website/app) after making a purchase there before the COVID epidemic (Zhao Huiliang et al., 2021). With the addition of satisfaction as a mediating variable, full mediation in the case of product pricing and partial mediation in the case of product packaging were observed. Given the findings of this study, product managers should use pricing strategies and product packaging to sway consumers'

purchasing decisions. M. Verma, B.R. Naveen (2021). The goal of this study is to identify the variables that affect consumers' purchasing decisions and to model those variables using partial least squares structural equation modelling to identify the causal relationship. The study's conclusions can help marketing managers create effective promotion plans to encourage ethnocentric tendencies, and they can give consumers clues to evoke feelings of economic nationalism when they purchase goods or services.

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- To identify the consumer motivations to shift from the brick to click channel of omnichannel supermarkets amidst COVID pandemic.
- To examine the influence of consumers' brick-to-click shift motivations on their satisfaction with the supermarket's online channel.
- To examine the influence of consumers' online shopping satisfaction on their perception of risk in shifting to the supermarket's online channel.
- To examine the influence of consumers' perceived risk in shifting to the supermarket's online channel on their online repeat purchase behaviour.
- To examine the influence consumers' online shopping satisfaction on their online repeat purchase behaviour.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H1: Avoidance of COVID infection has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction.

H2: In-home shopping convenience has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction.

H3: Website effectiveness has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction.

H4: Product value has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction.

H5: Customer service accountability has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction.

H6: Habitual loyalty has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction.

H7: Click and collect benefits has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction.

H8: Online shopping satisfaction has a negative effect on perceived risk in brick-to-click shift.

H9: Online shopping satisfaction has a positive effect on repeat purchase behaviour.

H10: Perceived risk in brick-to-click shift has a negative effect on repeat purchase behaviour.

The conceptual framework developed for this study consisting of the ten constructs and their hypothesized interrelationships is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for the Study

Validation of the Conceptual Framework

In order to validate the suggested conceptual framework, this study used Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) two-step modelling approach, which involved first estimating a confirmatory measurement model and then estimating a structural model. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to examine the measurement model's factor structure and validity, and the structural model (i.e., conceptual framework) was validated using the structural equation modelling (SEM) method with SPSS AMOS v26.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An effort is made to develop a suitable research methodology with the study's goals in mind. Utilizing a survey method based on questionnaires, the current investigation was carried out. 648 questionnaires in total were fully completed and used for this investigation. Secondary data for this study were gathered from journals, yearly reports, the library, internet information sources, bibliographies, conference proceedings, etc.

Sampling Procedure

All customers who had been purchasing online through omnichannel supermarket chains in Chennai during the COVID pandemic made up the target demographic of the current study. This study used a two-step sampling method, choosing stores in the first stage and choosing

shoppers from those supermarkets in the second stage. The Big Bazaar, SPAR Hypermarket, Kovai Pazhamudir Nilayam, and Grace Supermarket were the four supermarkets chosen by the researcher using the purposive sampling technique in the early stage. The supermarkets were chosen based on two criteria: (1) they were retail chains with numerous physical locations operating under one company or brand throughout the city; and (2) they were omnichannel in nature, employing and integrating multiple channels of shopping such as physical store, online, phone, etc. The selected omnichannel supermarket chains were widely popular in the areas their stores were present with considerable footfalls prior to the COVID pandemic. The list of customers who made purchases during July and August 2021 via the supermarkets' websites or apps was obtained from the supermarkets in the second stage. Every tenth client was contacted by phone and asked to participate in the survey to choose the respondents by systematic random sampling. If the client accepted, the self-report questionnaire was mailed to him or her, and an immediate follow-up was conducted to make sure the client completed the form. If not, the tenth consumer after that was chosen. The client list collected from all four supermarkets was put through this process several times until the necessary sample size was attained. Given that the respondents were chosen at random, these sampling strategies helped to some extent lessen the selection bias.

DATA COLLECTION

To gather information for the conceptual framework's empirical validation, a systematic questionnaire was created. Three components made up the questionnaire. The first section of the survey asked questions about the respondents' sociodemographic characteristics, while the second section focused on their shopping habits, including their relationship to supermarkets, frequency of purchases, preferred channels, percentage of online purchases, average price per purchase, and items bought. The scale items in the third section measured each construct in the suggested conceptual framework, including the brick-to-click shift reasons and their effects.

The motives scale provided by Priyadharshini and Sunitha (2022) was used to measure the seven brick-to-click shift motivations. Four independently developed items were used to gauge how satisfied customers were with their ability to shop online through the supermarket's website or mobile application. Six questions from perceived risk scales created by Han and Kim (2017) and Sunitha (2015) were used to analyse perceived risk in the brick-to-click transformation. Four items from the online repeat purchase behaviour scale developed by Rose et al. (2012) and Mortimer et al. were selected to measure repeat buy behaviour (2016). The Likert scale, with a maximum of 5, was used to rate these statements and objects on a scale of 1 to 5. The Appendix contains all of the measuring scales for all constructs.

Sample Size

During the data collection process, the customers were asked if they were willing to participate in the study. Their participation was completely voluntary and there were no incentives. The data were collected from the consumers via e-mail for a period of four months from September

to December 2021 in Chennai. Total of 519 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents and 458 fully completed were obtained for further data analysis.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used to determine how effectively the manifest/observed variables combined to represent the conceptual framework's latent constructs. Maximum likelihood (ML) estimation was used to perform CFA on the 46 manifest variables, which produced an acceptable solution and allayed any worries about the consequences of multicollinearity. The findings of the CFA revealed that the goodness-of-fit of the model was compromised since the standardised factor loadings of one item related to perceived risk in the brick-to-click shift construct were less than 0.5. As a result, this item was eliminated, and an estimation of the measurement model using the remaining 45 items was made. The findings demonstrated that all 45 items' standardised factor loadings, which ranged from 0.690 to 0.928, were significant and higher than the allowed limit of 0.5 (Hair et al., 2006). Also, the item squared multiple correlations (SMCs) ranged from 0.476 to 0.861 and all modification indices were low and insignificant. Hence, no additional items were removed from the measurement model.

AVE and CR estimations were the additional criteria for assessing convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The structures' CR values varied from 0.873 to 0.942, exceeding the required cutoff point of 0.7, indicating strong internal consistency (Hair et al., 2006). As shown in Table 3, the AVE values of the constructs ranged from 0.580 to 0.804, exceeding the threshold of 0.5 that established appropriate convergent validity (Hair et al., 2006).

By contrasting the AVEs with the correlations between the constructs in a correlation matrix, as shown in Table 4, the discriminant validity was evaluated. All of the constructs were judged to have sufficient discriminant validity because their AVEs were higher than their corresponding squared correlations (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 3: Confirmatory Factor Analysis - Reliability and Validity Assessment

Dimensions	Statements (You shifted to the online shopping channel of the supermarket because...)	Factor Loadings	Average Variance Extracted	Composite Reliability
Avoidance of COVID Infection	To avoid meeting people in supermarket	0.822	0.629	0.894
	To avoid picking groceries myself which can cause infection	0.740		
	To avoid spending time in supermarket during pandemic	0.766		
	To avoid meeting shop personnel due to higher risk of infection	0.771		
	To avoid worry about wearing masks and sanitizing myself	0.860		
In-home Shopping Convenience	Online shopping can be done safely from home	0.818	0.636	0.875
	Shopping online saves a lot of time	0.802		
	There is no time limitation while shopping online	0.821		
	I am spared the hassle of commuting to supermarket	0.747		

Website Effectiveness	Website/app is well-designed to reduce time wastage	0.841	0.712	0.925
	It is quick and easy to complete transaction on website/app	0.848		
	Website/app has a good selection of brands and products	0.836		
	I can efficiently browse & compare products on website/app	0.830		
	I can add items in e-cart and order anytime	0.864		
Product Value	It provides high quality products	0.810	0.634	0.874
	The products are reasonably priced	0.774		
	It offers a wide variety of products	0.844		
	It provides good offers and discounts	0.755		
Customer Service Accountability	The employees handle complaints, returns and exchanges efficiently	0.811	0.580	0.873
	I can contact the supermarket easily in case of any product issues	0.792		
	The customer service employees are empathetic and courteous	0.699		
	The employees take accountability in case of problems	0.756		
	The customer service is very prompt and personalized	0.745		
Habitual Loyalty	I always purchase groceries from this supermarket	0.881	0.657	0.884
	It is preferable place to buy groceries in this area	0.766		
	I feel uncomfortable to purchase groceries from any other store	0.815		
	I have known this supermarket and its staff for years	0.776		
Click and Collect Benefits	It offers CC service that allows me to collect order anytime	0.807	0.658	0.905
	CC transaction is quick for collecting/returning order	0.821		
	I need not pay delivery charges for CC service	0.791		
	I need not fear that returns will be rejected with CC service	0.732		
	Its CC service offers pleasure of offline shopping with selection done online	0.895		
Online Shopping Satisfaction	I got the same satisfaction as store shopping	0.886	0.804	0.942
	I am satisfied with my overall online shopping experience using this supermarket's website/app	0.905		
	I do not have any inhibitions in online shopping using this supermarket's website/app	0.896		
	My pandemic fears have been overcome because of supermarket's online option	0.899		
Perceived Risk in Brick to Click Shift	I am concerned that I am unable to browse a wide range of products online	0.928	0.634	0.895
	I am concerned that the products delivered will be of inferior quality	0.868		

	I am concerned that my personal and card details would be stolen	0.751		
	I am concerned that it may take long time to deliver the products	0.693		
	I am concerned that not many people will choose to shop online	0.716		
Repeat Purchase Behaviour	I consider this supermarket's website/app as my first choice to buy	0.907	0.653	0.881
	I regularly purchase from this supermarket's website/app	0.764		
	Even after pandemic, I will continue using website/app along with store visits	0.690		
	I expect to repurchase from this supermarket's website/app in the near future	0.853		

Table 4: Confirmatory Factor Analysis - Discriminant Validity

Constructs	COVID	CON	WEB	PVAL	CSA	HLOY	CCB	SAT	RISK	RPB
COVID	0.629									
CON	0.013	0.636								
WEB	0.203	0.286	0.712							
PVAL	0.008	0.016	0.043	0.634						
CSA	0.246	0.075	0.318	0.002	0.580					
HLOY	0.059	0.030	0.023	0.014	0.050	0.657				
CCB	0.002	0.434	0.251	0.001	0.066	0.023	0.658			
SAT	0.100	0.199	0.334	0.138	0.046	0.069	0.124	0.804		
RISK	0.064	0.089	0.118	0.027	0.117	0.015	0.077	0.051	0.634	
RPB	0.095	0.028	0.084	0.006	0.078	0.003	0.032	0.095	0.112	0.653

Note: Diagonal elements in bold are AVE estimates; non-diagonal elements are squared correlations between the constructs;

COVID- avoidance of COVID infection, CON- in-home shopping convenience, WEB- website effectiveness, PVAL- product value, CSA- customer service accountability, HLOY- habitual loyalty, CCB- click and collect benefits, SAT- online shopping satisfaction, RISK- perceived risk in brick-to-click shift, RPB- repeat purchase behaviour

The measurement model had adequate model fit ($\chi^2(900) = 2364.46, p = .00; GFI = .826; CFI = .901; NFI = .850; IFI = .901; RMSEA = .058$) (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003). Figure 2 presents the measurement model consisting of ten factors and 45 manifest variables obtained after validity and reliability assessment during confirmatory factor analysis.

Figure 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis - Measurement Model

Structural Equation Modelling

The structural model was built using the measurement model that was validated and estimated during the earlier stage of Confirmatory Factor Analysis. The model was constructed using ten latent variables and 45 observed/manifest variables as indicators of their respective latent variables derived from the measurement model. They were interrelated to each other as hypothesized in the conceptual framework.

The SEM estimation was run to validate the proposed conceptual framework. This process included reviewing the path coefficients of linkages and squared multiple correlations (R²) for each endogenous variable in the structural model. The path/regression coefficients represent the strength and significance of the relationship between variables, and R² values denote the amount of variance explained in endogenous variables by their predictor variables. The SEM estimation results showed that nine out of ten hypothesized relationships were validated with significant path coefficients and p-values, whereas one relationship was insignificant since p-

value was greater than 0.05. A summary of the significant relationships in the structural model along with their unstandardized and standardized regression weights i.e., path coefficients are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Regression Coefficients of Relationships in Structural Model

Relationships			Unstd. Regression Weights	Std. Regression Weights	p-value
COVID	--->	SAT	0.214	0.139	0.004
CON	--->	SAT	0.341	0.288	0.000
WEB	--->	SAT	0.444	0.408	0.000
PV	--->	SAT	0.225	0.218	0.000
CS	--->	SAT	0.277	0.218	0.000
HLOY	--->	SAT	0.323	0.238	0.000
SAT	--->	RISK	-0.253	-0.239	0.000
SAT	--->	RPB	0.243	0.245	0.000
RISK	--->	RPB	-0.260	-0.277	0.000

Note: COVID- avoidance of COVID infection, CON- in-home shopping convenience, WEB- website effectiveness, PVAL- product value, CSA- customer service accountability, HLOY- habitual loyalty, CCB- click and collect benefits, SAT- online shopping satisfaction, RISK- perceived risk in brick-to-click shift, RPB- repeat purchase behaviour

An examination of path coefficients revealed that website effectiveness emerged as the strongest brick-to-click shift motivation influencing online shopping satisfaction of the respondents with a significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.404$, $p < 0.01$) which was also found to be the strongest linkage in the structural model. This implies that the extent to which the respondents perceived the supermarket's website/app as effective in terms of its quality, design, navigation, product range, information search ability and ease of ordering and payment determines their online shopping satisfaction.

The in-home shopping convenience was found to be the second strongest motivation for the brick-to-click shift with significant positive effect on online shopping satisfaction ($\beta = 0.288$, $p < 0.01$) followed by habitual loyalty ($\beta = 0.238$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that a crucial factor in the respondents' happiness with their online buying is their sense of the ease afforded by online shopping in terms of place and time flexibility, lowering their shopping effort, and saving time and money. Additionally, the findings indicate that habitual loyalty—defined as respondents' propensity to shop at supermarkets as a habit or regular activity of their daily routine—significantly affects customer happiness. This suggests that customers who often purchase at a supermarket are more likely to be pleased with their online shopping experience.

Product value and customer service accountability were the other brick-to-click shift motivations which had a significant positive effect on online shopping satisfaction ($\beta = 0.218$, $p < 0.01$). The respondents' perception of product value and customer service accountability of the supermarket formed by their past shopping experiences emerged as crucial motives for the brick-to-click shift which significantly influenced consumers' satisfaction with online

shopping via the supermarket's website/app. Besides, the avoidance of COVID infection, a fundamental motive for the brick-to-click shift also had a significant positive effect on online shopping satisfaction ($\beta = 0.139$, $p < 0.01$). This indicates that the respondents who were more inclined to online shopping to avoid COVID infection were found to be more satisfied with the online shopping experience using the supermarket's website/app.

Since its p-value was higher than 0.05, click and collect advantages was the only brick-to-click shift motive that was not discovered to have a significant beneficial effect on online shopping satisfaction. This suggests that the click and collect option provided by the supermarkets did not materially increase the respondents' happiness with online shopping done through the supermarket's website or app. One of the causes of this non-importance could be that only a small number of study participants used the click and collect (Buy-Online-Pickup-in-Store) service.

With regards to the consequences, online shopping satisfaction had a significant negative effect on perceived risk in brick-to-click shift ($\beta = -0.239$, $p < 0.01$). This finding validates that the respondents who are satisfied with the online shopping experience perceive lower risk in shifting to the online shopping channel of the supermarket. Likewise, online shopping satisfaction had a significant positive effect on repeat purchase behaviour ($\beta = 0.245$, $p < 0.01$). This implies that respondents who were more satisfied with their online shopping experience have a higher likelihood to continue using the supermarket's website/app, thereby validating the classic customer satisfaction-loyalty relationship in marketing literature. Besides, perceived risk in brick-to-click shift emerged as a significant negative predictor of repeat purchase behaviour ($\beta = -0.277$, $p < 0.01$). This signifies that the respondents who perceived lower risk in shifting to the online shopping channel of the supermarket had stronger intentions to continue purchasing through the supermarket's website/app.

Overall, the model estimation results produced six significant antecedents (i.e., avoiding COVID infection, in-home shopping convenience, website effectiveness, product value, customer service accountability, habitual loyalty) and two significant consequences of online shopping satisfaction (i.e., perceived risk in brick-to-click shift and repeat purchase behaviour). Therefore, six of the seven brick-to-click shift reasons that were postulated in the COVID analysis directly impacted consumer satisfaction with online purchasing and indirectly influenced their propensity to make repeat purchases.

The SEM estimated using maximum likelihood (ML) method was found to have adequate model fit ($\chi^2(716) = 1919.59$, $p = .00$; GFI = .836; CFI = .906; NFI = .858; IFI = 0.906; RMSEA = .059) indicating that the proposed model fit the data reasonably well. The assessment of squared multiple correlations (R²) revealed that the structural model explained 51 percent of the variance in online shopping satisfaction construct, 17 percent of the variance in repeat purchase behaviour and only 6 percent of the variance in perceived risk in brick-to-click shift construct. The fundamental reason for the statistically lower R² value for the two consequences is that there were only one or two direct predictors, unlike online shopping satisfaction which was linked to seven antecedents leading to higher explained variance. Based

on the notion that a large number of factors might influence these constructs in real world, the amount of variance explained by the model was considered reasonable.

The SEM path diagram with the estimation results obtained from SPSS AMOS v26 is presented in Figure 6.6 which include the standardized direct effects for the paths/relationships between the constructs, factor loadings between the latent and manifest variables and squared multiple correlations for both endogenous variables and manifest variables.

Figure 3: Structural Equation Modelling - Estimation Results

The model estimation process of the proposed conceptual framework using SEM resulted in the validation of nine out of ten hypothesized relationships as presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Hypotheses Testing of Relationships – Results

	Hypotheses	Path Coefficients	Supported/ Not supported
H1	Avoidance of COVID infection has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction	0.139**	Supported
H2	In-home shopping convenience has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction	0.288**	Supported
H3	Website effectiveness has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction	0.408**	Supported
H4	Product value has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction	0.218**	Supported
H5	Customer service accountability has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction	0.218**	Supported
H6	Habitual loyalty has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction	0.238**	Supported
H7	Click and collect benefits has a positive effect on online shopping satisfaction	-	Not supported
H8	Online shopping satisfaction has a negative effect on perceived risk in brick-to-click shift	-0.239**	Supported
H9	Online shopping satisfaction has a positive effect on repeat purchase behaviour	0.245**	Supported
H10	Perceived risk in brick-to-click shift has a negative effect on repeat purchase behaviour	-0.277**	Supported

Note: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$

CONCLUSION

The success of online shopping depends on customers' repeat purchasing. This study proposed a theoretical model by integrating the literature of expectation–confirmation model and online shopping to test the factors affecting repeat purchase intention in online group-buying. Data collected from 458 respondents were used to test the proposed model. The model estimation results yielded six significant antecedents of online shopping satisfaction (i.e., avoidance of COVID infection, in-home shopping convenience, website effectiveness, product value, customer service accountability, habitual loyalty) and two significant consequences of online shopping satisfaction (i.e., perceived risk in brick-to-click shift and repeat purchase behaviour). Thus, six out of seven proposed brick-to-click shift motivations amidst COVID pandemic directly affected consumers' online shopping satisfaction and indirectly influenced their repeat purchase behaviour.

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

In the context of trust-satisfaction-repurchase intention in the omni channel supermarket, this study examines the considerable impact of brick-to-click shift on consumers' online repeat purchase behaviour as well as the moderating effect of consumers' neurotic tendencies. Additionally, a combination of structural equation models (SEM) and prediction-oriented

segmentation (POS) was used to uncover the likely underlying heterogeneous traits of consumers. The results of the global model SEM analysis show that offline-to-online trust transference occurs in e-commerce and that this transference of trust greatly affects consumers' pleasure and their propensity to make repeat purchases. Customers' pleasure with their online purchasing was directly impacted by six out of the seven postulated brick-to-click shift reasons during the COVID epidemic, and their subsequent purchase behaviour was indirectly influenced.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This study adopted a two-stage sampling technique, in the initial stage, the researcher employed purposive sampling technique to select four supermarkets in Chennai i.e., Big Bazaar, SPAR Hypermarket, Kovai Pazhamudir Nilayam and Grace Supermarket. In the second stage, the list of consumers who made purchases during July and August 2021 through the supermarkets' website or app were acquired from the supermarkets. The selection was based on the criteria that the supermarkets were (1) retail chains with multiple physical stores across the city operating under the one company/brand and (2) omni channel in nature i.e., employing and integrating multiple channels of shopping such as physical store, online, phone, etc. The selected omni channel supermarket chains were widely popular in the areas their stores were present with considerable footfalls prior to the COVID pandemic. Future research studies were consider to select other supermarkets, malls, local markets etc. This study was conducted during the pandemic period in Chennai, future studies may conduct any other specific period and consumers from various locations.

References

1. Aaker, D.A. (1991). *Managing brand equity: Capitalizing on the value of a brand name*, New York, The Free Press
2. Agnihotri, A. (2015). Can Brick-and-Mortar Retailers Successfully Become Multichannel Retailers?. *Journal of Marketing Channels*, 22(1), 62-73.
3. Ankita Sharma, & Mita Mehta. (2020). *Effect Of Covid-19 Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Cosmetics: Study Based On Working Females*. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt / Egyptology*, 17(9), 5155 - 5175.
4. Baicu, C.G., Gârdan, I. P., Gârdan, D.A., Epuran, G., (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on consumer behavior in retail banking. Evidence from Romania. *Management & Marketing. Challenges for the Knowledge Society*, 15, 534-556.
6. Charu Bisaria (2021). *Impact Of Covid-19 On Consumer Behaviour*. *Revista de Investigaciones Universidad del Quindío, Universidad del Quindío, Colombi*, 33(2), 2021
7. Curtis, T., Abratt, R., Rhoades, D. L., & Dion, P. (2011). Customer Loyalty, Repurchase and Satisfaction: A Meta-Analytical Review. *Journal of Consumer Satisfaction, Dissatisfaction and Complaining Behavior*, 24.
8. Debnath, S. (2020). *Impact of COVID-19 on Consumer Purchase Behaviour in Retail Sector - Study Based in Kolkata Area*. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3634598

9. Laato, Samuli, Islam, A.K.M. Najmul, Farooq, Ali & Dhir, Amandeep, (2020). Unusual purchasing behavior during the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic: The stimulus-organism-response approach. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Elsevier, 57(C).
10. Li, Z. (Erick), Lu, Q., & Talebian, M. (2014). Online versus bricks-and-mortar retailing: a comparison of price, assortment and delivery time. *International Journal of Production Research*, 53(13), 1-14.
11. Luo, L., & Sun, J. (2016). New Product Design under Channel Acceptance: Brick-and-Mortar, Online-Exclusive, or Brick-and-Click. *Production and Operations Management*, 25(12), 2014-2034.
12. Marmol, M., & Fernandez, V. (2019). Trigger factors in brick and click shopping. *Intangible Capital*, 15(1), 57-71.
13. Pathak, G., & Warpade, S. (2020). Impact of Lockdown Due to COVID-19 on Consumer Behaviour While Selecting Retailer for Essential Goods. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=366457
14. Rajeswari, P & Vijai, C.. (2020). The Impact of COVID-19 on Consumers behavior in India, 45, 2249-6661.
15. Sheth J. (2020). Impact of Covid-19 on consumer behavior: Will the old habits return or die? *Journal of business research*, 117, 280–283.
16. Svajdova, L. (2021). Consumer Behaviour during Pandemic of COVID-19. *Journal of International Business Research and Marketing*, 6(3), 34-37.
17. Tao Hu, Sun Xin, Liu Xia, Tian Jinfang, Zhang Di (2022). The Impact of Consumer Purchase Behavior Changes on the Business Model Design of Consumer Services Companies Over the Course of COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13.
18. Ulpiano J. Vázquez-Martínez, Javier Morales-Mediano, Antonio L. Leal-Rodríguez, (2021). The impact of the COVID-19 crisis on consumer purchasing motivation and behavior, *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 27(3).
19. Verma, M., & Naveen, B. R. (2021). COVID-19 Impact on Buying Behaviour. *Vikalpa: The Journal for Decision Makers*, 46(1), 27–40.
20. Zhao, H., Yao, X., Liu, Z., & Yang, Q. (2021). Impact of Pricing and Product Information on Consumer Buying Behavior With Customer Satisfaction in a Mediating Role. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 720151.